

AI-driven detection of skin-related neglected tropical diseases

The project is supported by Global Health EDCTP3 and its members.

Co-funded by the European Union

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Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
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The image features a dark purple background with two large, stylized white handprints. The handprints are positioned on the left and right sides, with their fingers pointing towards the center. The text is centered between the two handprints.

Bringing together African and European partners to fight skin-related neglected tropical diseases in Sub-Saharan Africa through an AI-powered mobile app designed for frontline health workers.

The Vision

SkincAIr envisions a world where early detection of skin-related Neglected Tropical Diseases (NTDs) is accessible, accurate, and ethically powered by artificial intelligence.

By equipping frontline health workers with inclusive, context-aware technology, we strive to improve health equity in underserved communities across Sub-Saharan Africa.

SkincAIr's mission is to develop and scale an AI-powered mobile application that enhances the diagnostic capabilities of Front-line Health Workers (FHWs), supports real-time epidemiological surveillance, and fosters inclusive digital health innovation. SkincAIr aims to build the largest open-access dataset of skin NTDs, driving early intervention, improved care, and informed health policy across five countries in Sub-Saharan Africa.

The Mission

About skin-related neglected tropical diseases

Neglected Tropical Diseases (NTDs) are a group of diseases endemic in 149 countries and estimated to affect over 1 billion people worldwide, many of them children. NTDs predominantly affect impoverished people who live in rural and hard-to-reach areas where access to safe water, sanitation, and essential medicines is lacking.

Skin NTDs are a subgroup of NTDs that can present with manifestation on the skin. Skin NTDs are often associated with lifelong disabilities, stigma and mental health problems.

Endemic in

149

countries

Over

1B

people affected
worldwide

A major healthcare issue

In Sub-Saharan African, skin NTDs affect millions, causing chronic health problems – here's why:

500M

AFFECTED

One third of the population
in Sub-Saharan Africa
suffers from a skin NTD

138K

ANNUAL DEATHS

They are the third most
prevalent cause of illness and
one of the top 10 causes of
disability

1

DERMATOLOGIST PER

2M

PEOPLE

Skin NTDs are often
underreported or are
not included in routine
surveillance systems

The consequences

Skin NTDs aggravate health inequalities and heavily impact marginalized communities

Patients have to contend with stigma, isolation and discrimination in their daily life

Skin NTDs contribute widely to Higher morbidity and disability rates

Channeling the Power of AI Against Skin NTDs

Our mission is to address these challenges head-on by putting AI-powered tools directly in the hands of frontline health workers—those closest to the patient. SkincAIr will develop novel AI models for detection and prediction, enabling early diagnosis, fostering regional NTD advocacy, and strengthening real-time epidemiological surveillance.

By bridging the gap between underserved populations and access to timely, accurate diagnosis and surveillance, SkincAIr will lay the foundation for more equitable, effective, and sustainable care for skin NTDs.

Our value proposition

**An AI-driven app for
early detection of skin
NTDs**

**The largest public skin
NTD dataset**

The ultimate goal

Increase Health Security in
Sub-Saharan Africa

Improve training and
knowledge-transfer to
front-line workers

Reduce the socio-economic
burden of skin NTDs
in Sub-Saharan Africa

Who we are?

Begins here in SSA

1/3 SSA with NTDs
500 Million
138.000 death/Year

1 dermatologist
per 2 million inhabitants

Health inequities,
marginalized
communities

Stigma isolation
discrimination

High Morbidity
disability

What are our goals?

Early
Detection of
skin-NTDs

Epidemiologic
al Surveillance

Novel Detection
and Prediction
Models of
Artificial
Intelligence

Digital
Solution is
culturally
tailored

Reduce
Transmission

Education and
Knowledge
Transfer to
Front-line Health
Workers

NTDs
Advocacy

Outcomes & Impacts

AI-powered skin care
in the palm of your hand

Completing the Puzzle for the Largest-ever Dataset on Skin NTDs

The data goal

3,500

High-resolution images of skin NTDs with depth and scaling information, clinical and epidemiological data

12

Hospitals involved for data labelling, annotation, diagnosis check and image segmentation

SkincAir is conducting a large-scale data collection exercise with the aim of developing an innovative, AI-driven mobile application for detecting and predicting skin Neglected Tropical Diseases (NTDs).

The resulting dataset will encompass tabular data (e.g. patient demographics, medical history, and treatment details), images, and geospatial inputs. A harmonised electronic Case Report Form (eCRF) will ensure uniformity in the type and format of the data collected for the validation study and piloting on the ground.

Anonymized
patient information

Patient
categories

Our metadata dictionary

Image details

Clinical data on diagnosis,
prognosis and treatment

Annotation details

AI Models for Early Detection, Prognosis & Treatment of Skin NTDs

AI-powered diagnostic support

Fair and inclusive model

Smart and scalable tech

A Reliable, Flexible Mobile App for Frontline Health Workers

The power to detect, monitor and manage skin NTDs from your own device

Real-time
image capture

Augmented
detection

QR code generation
for easy access

Dedicated
training resources &
capacity building

A close-up profile of a person's face, partially obscured by vertical blinds. The person's eyes are looking towards the right. The text "Our process at a glance" is overlaid in white, bold, sans-serif font across the center of the image.

**Our process
at a glance**

Together for a Better Standard of Care

A co-designed, scalable AI solution to strengthen skin NTD care across Sub-Saharan Africa

The SkincAIr project is built around a robust, participatory methodology that integrates cutting-edge technology with local expertise to improve the detection and management of skin-related neglected tropical diseases (NTDs).

Our solutions are co-developed with stakeholders in five implementation countries: Kenya, Senegal, Ethiopia, Nigeria, and the Democratic Republic of the Congo, ensuring it responds to real needs and regional healthcare priorities.

The fight against skin NTDs

Our methodology is grounded in five interconnected pillars:

A cornerstone for
User-Centric Co-Design

Tailored AI Model
Development and Fine-tuning

Resilient Mobile App
Deployment

Geotagging &
Data Privacy

Capacity Building &
Policy Alignment

Our Pilot Countries

Taking action through local, community-driven AI

SkincAIr will be implemented in five countries (Kenya, Senegal, Ethiopia, Nigeria and the Democratic Republic of the Congo), each facing high socio-economic burdens of skin NTDs and significant barriers to early diagnosis.

In each country, local clinics and health research institutions will support the deployment and testing of the app. These sites will also contribute to the creation of the first public dataset of skin NTDs images in Sub-Saharan Africa, and help validate the AI models under real clinical conditions.

The methodology for this large scale piloting exercise will follow three distinct phases.

Phase 1

Design methodology & cultural adequacy

STEP 1
Initial
fieldwork

STEP 2
Design
methodology
application

STEP 3
Cultural
adequacy
assessment

STEP 4
Detailed
design
specifications

STEP 5
Concept
validation

STEP 6
Design
iterations

Phase 2

Clinical data collection

STEP 1
Ad hoc
training

STEP 2
Study
initiation
package

STEP 3
Open
dataset
construction

STEP 4
Continuous
feedback
loop

Phase 3

App launch, validation & performance check

STEP 1
SkincAir app
introduction
and
validation

STEP 2
Continuation
of the user
research

STEP 3
Scale up and
expansion

STEP 4
Geospatial
analysis

SkincAir

Our consortium

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12
PARTNERS

10
COUNTRIES

5
YEARS

Thank you

Global Health
EDCTP3

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